

Adverse soils tolerance

Screening for salinity tolerance by rapid generation advance

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Considerable intravarietal variation in levels of salinity tolerance of rice varieties has been reported. We sought to improve salt tolerance by selecting within crosses and parents and comparing progress over five generations.

One hundred eighty seeds of each variety or cross (see figure) were closely spaced in plastic basins 25 cm in diam × 20 cm deep, filled with mangrove soil. Four weeks after sowing, the plants were subjected to 60 mM NaCl concentration for 2 wk by submerging the basins in salt solution. After exposure to salt, the plants were induced to flower by shortening the day length to 8 h for 2 wk. Surviving plants (tillers) were grown to maturity. Seeds of each variety or cross were harvested and bulked for use in the next generation. The cycle was repeated for three more generations (F₃-F₅).

F₆ seeds of each cross were grown in three 5-m rows at 25- × 25-cm spacing in a saline mangrove swamp. Forty kg N/ha was applied as urea by injection. Selection of suitable genotypes was primarily by tiller number/plant.

Results indicated that successive generations could be grown continuously and only plants that are highly or moderately tolerant of salt will survive to go to the next generation (see figure). Highly sensitive individuals died after exposure to 60 mM NaCl solutions for 2 wk. Mean salt tolerance of all the varieties or crosses increased with each generation, but the degree of tolerance was significantly different (F = 7.1, P<0.01 for tiller number, and F = 6.5, P<0.01 for number of filled grains).

Varietal response to selection for salinity tolerance during rapid generation advance. Vertical bar represents the LSD (P < 0.05) between any two points. Correlation coefficient = (r = 0.86 dF = 34 P < 0.001) between tiller number and total grain number.

Field performance of F₆ plants from the greenhouse test. Readings were taken on selected plants only.

Cross	Selected plants (no.)	Mean tillers (no.)	Range of tillers (no./plant)
Pokkali/Djabon	7	18.4	13-26
Pa Fant 213/Rok 10	9	20.6	14-32
Improved Mahsuri/Rice Mill	35	15.8	11-27

Selection for other characters like plant height and tiller number per plant was not possible during rapid generation advance because of the narrow range within which varieties were distributed. Selection for suitable morphological char-

acters is only possible in the saline swamp in subsequent generations (F₆-F₇), where selection should be easier because only nearly fixed lines would be available. The range of various characters of F₆ plants (see table) grown in the field showed that

the variability was not lost over several generations of selfing in the rapid generation process. Rapid generation speeded the cycle without affecting individual plant potential for other morphological characters. □

Evaluation of some elite rice cultures for intercropping on Oxisols in coconut gardens

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Most coconut gardens in Kerala are planted on sloping terrain on Oxisols. Because 85% of the gardens are rainfed, coconut and long-duration perennial intercrops such as banana, cassava, and pineapple suffer severe moisture stress from Dec to May. Planting short-duration crops like upland rice during the monsoon (Jun-Nov) may reduce competition between coconut and intercrops for soil moisture. Upland rice cultivation in the rainfed coconut gardens could be lucrative, with suitable varieties and management practices.

Seven rice cultivars from the Central Rice Research Institute and one local cultivar (see table) were grown in a randomized block design in a coconut

Yield data of upland rice intercropped with coconut. 1980 kharif.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Sterility (%)	Harvest index	Duration (d)
CR143-2-2	4.5	205	79	27	22	0.98	103
MW10	4.5	212	79	27	12	0.97	103
CR16 2-2	3.4	196	73	24	12	1.28	96
AUS61	4.2	114	184	20	15	0.59	109
BG35-2	3.7	181	63	31	43	0.62	109
CtG1516	4.2	186	94	24	9	0.94	96
ARC7001	3.7	204	61	26	27	0.69	96
Local check	2.1	218	37	29	25	0.55	99
LSD (0.05)	967.5	NS	18.8	1.9	1.9	15.14	0.05

^a Sowing date = 6 Sep 1980. Spacing = 20 × 10 cm. Plot size (harvested) = 3.4 × 1.6 m. Soil pH was 5.5 (0-30 cm depth). Rainfall in Jun, Jul, Aug, and Sep 1980 was 1369, 1325, 611, and 115 mm. Normal rainfall is 944, 1117, 599, and 262 mm.

garden with 40-year-old palms spaced 8 × 8 m at Kottamparamba (11° 15'N, 75° 52' E, altitude 80 m above sea level) 1980 monsoon. Plot size was 4 × 2 m. Farmyard manure at 5,000 kg/ha, lime at 250, N at 40, P at 20, and K at 20 were applied. NPK was applied in equal splits 15 and 30 d after sowing, both applications in combination with hand weeding. Bunds were opened to minimize standing

water. Appropriate insect controls were used. Rice was harvested in Sep.

CR143-2-2, MW10, AUS61, and CtG1516 yielded more than 4 t/ha (see table), twice that of the local check. Although the data are for 1 year only, the study indicates the wide scope for adopting suitable rice varieties for intercropping in coconut-based cropping systems. □

Performance of rice varieties in sodic soils

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We assessed tolerance levels of varieties P2-21, Jaya, IR8, and CSRI to highly sodic soils at Gudda Research Farm and to semireclaimed sodic soils at Karnal in 1982 kharif. Soil at Gudda was a sandy loam with pH 10.5, 92% exchangeable sodium, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.4 meq/100 g, 0.23% organic carbon, and cation exchange capacity 9.0 meq/100 g. Soil at Karnal was a sandy loam, with pH 8.7, 10% exchangeable sodium, exchangeable Ca + Mg 7.50 meq/100 g, 1.30% CaCO₃,

Relative performance of rice varieties in sodic and semireclaimed sodic soil.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (m)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (m)	pH after rice harvest ^a		% reduction of grain yield
					0-15 cm	15-30 cm	
<i>Semireclaimed sodic soil^a in Karnal</i>							
Jaya	7.2	92.7	9.6	21.3	8.5	8.8	—
IR8	7.5	98.8	9.8	21.1	8.5	8.7	—
P2-21	6.4	87.6	9.6	20.3	8.6	8.8	—
CSRI	4.5	136.6	9.5	19.4	8.5	8.7	—
CD (P = 0.05)	0.4	3.6	NS	1.5			
<i>Sodic soil at Gudda</i>							
Jaya	0.8	56.4	7.5	15.4	10.2	10.3	89
IR8	0.7	57.2	7.6	15.5	10.2	10.2	90
P2-21	0.8	64.5	7.4	15.6	10.1	10.3	87
CSRI	1.7	90.4	10.4	15.6	10.1	10.2	66
CD (P = 0.05)	0.04	4.8	1.3	NS	—	—	—

^a Initial pH (0-15 cm) was 8.7 for semireclaimed sodic soil and 10.5 for sodic soil.